

Collection of Data Publications generated by H2020 Project 'iAtlantic' (Grant: 818123) - Result of the 1st Data Publications Inventory (completed: 10 June 2022)

iAtlantic Data ID	Dataset - Full Citation	Main Dataset - Persistent Identifier URL	Datasets bundled in Main - Persistent Identifier
IATL_DATA_0001	Biaستoch, A, Schwarzkopf, F. U., Getzlaff, K., Rűhs, S., Martin, T., Scheinert, M., Schulzki, T., Handmann, P., Hummels, R., and Claus W. Bűning: Supplementary Data to Biaستoch et al. (2021): Regional Imprints of Changes in the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation in the Eddy-rich Ocean Model VIKING20X [data set], available at: https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12085/a8f98a1a-473f-11ea-a036-c81f66eb46c3	https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12085/a8f98a1a-473f-11ea-a036-c81f66eb46c3	
IATL_DATA_0002	Burmeister, Kristin; Lűbbecke, Joke; Brandt, Peter; Claus, Martin; Hahn, Johannes (2019): Ventilation of the eastern tropical North Atlantic by intraseasonal flow events of the North Equatorial Undercurrent. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.903913	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.903913	
IATL_DATA_0003	Burmeister, Kristin; Lűbbecke, Joke; Brandt, Peter; Duteil, Olaf (2019): Interannual variability of the Atlantic North Equatorial Undercurrent and its impact on	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.899052	
IATL_DATA_0004	Charo, Marcela; Guerrero, Raul; Piola, Alberto, 2020, "Subtropical Shelf Front cruise - Conductivity-Temperature-Depth (CTD data)", https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/IHWLL3 , Harvard	https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/IHWLL3	
IATL_DATA_0005	Chiessi, Cristiano Mazur; Muiltza, Stefan; Taniguchi, Nancy Kazumi; Prange, Matthias; Campos, Marfília de Carvalho; Hűggi, Christoph; Schefuű, Enno; Pinho, Tainű Marcos Lima; Frederichs, Thomas; Portilho-Ramos, Rodrigo Costa; Sousa, Sílvia Helena; Crivellari, Stefano; Cruz, Francisco William (2020): Radiocarbon age, geochemical and physical parameters of sediment core	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.921255	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.921253 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.921254
IATL_DATA_0006	Combes Magali, Vaz Sandrine (2019). Systematic conservation planning for the North-Atlantic deep sea. SEANOE. https://doi.org/10.17882/62541	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541	
IATL_DATA_0007	Dominguez-Carriű, Carlos, Taranto, Gerald H., Ramos, Manuela, Ocaűa, Oscar Vicente, Fauconnet, Laurence, Gonçaves, Emanuel J., Carreiro-Silva, Marina, & Morato, Telmo. (2021). Blue Azores Program Expedition 2018, Station 57, Dive 15: annotation of Paragorgia johnsoni	www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4727163	
IATL_DATA_0008	Frűhberg, Nico; Paul, Sophie Anna Luise (2021): Porewater oxygen profiles in surface sediments of the North Atlantic Basin during RV Maria S. Merian cruise	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.931647	
IATL_DATA_0009	Gazis, Iason-Zois; Mohrmann, Jochen; Schoening, Timm; Wűfl, Anne-Cathrin (2021): Multibeam bathymetry processed data (Kongsberg EM 122 working area dataset) of RV MARIA S. MERIAN during cruise MSM96. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.930063	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.930063	
IATL_DATA_0010	González-Irusta, José Manuel; Fauconnet, Laurence; Das, Diya; Catarino, Diana; Afonso, Pedro; Viegas, Clűdia Neto; Rodrigues, Luís; Menezes, Gui; Rosa, Alexandra; Pinho, Műrio Rui Rilhű; Silva, Hűlder Marques da; Giacomello, Eva; Morato, Telmo (2022): Outputs of predictive distribution models of deep-sea elasmobranchs in the Azores EEZ (down to 2,000m depth)	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.940808	
IATL_DATA_0011	Gould, W. John; Cunningham, Stuart (2021). Specific gravity (density) measurements taken from the HMS Challenger and SMS Gazelle in the global ocean from 1873-02-15 to 1876-06-05 (NCEI Accession 0228229). [indicate subset used]. NOAA National Centers for Environmental	https://doi.org/10.25921/icca-e972	
IATL_DATA_0012	Hebbeln, Dierk (2019): ROV-CTD data from RV Meteor cruise M122 in 2016 off Angola. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.904187	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.904187	
IATL_DATA_0013	Hennige SJet al.2021Physical and modelled interactions between coral growth and water hydrodynamics using Lophelia pertusa as a model organism. NERC EDS British Oceanographic	https://doi.org/10/gnm9	
IATL_DATA_0014	Hoving, Henk-Jan Ties; Christiansen, Svenja; Hauss, Helena; Neitzel, Philipp; Kiko, Rainer; Robison, Bruce H; Silva, Pericles; Kűrtzinger, Arne (2020): Annotation data of video collected during Maria S. Merian cruise MSM49 with the pelagic in situ observation system (PELAGIOS).	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.919335	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.919333 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.919334
IATL_DATA_0015	Hutchinson, Katherine; Henry, Tahlia; Luyt, Hermann; Bournman, Tommy; Burger, Jessica; Flynn, Raquel; Reuben Audh, Riesna; Smith, Shantelle; Spence, Kurt, Fawcett, Sarah (2019). CTD data from the Weddell Sea Expedition 2019 (Version 1) [Data set]. Zenodo.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3357972	

IATL_DATA_0016	Kaufmann, Manfred; Springer, Barbara; Krahnmann, Gerd; Christiansen, Bernd (2020): Physical oceanography during Maria S. Merian cruise MSM49. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910346	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910346	
IATL_DATA_0017	Kazanidis, Georgios; Henry, Lea-Anne; Vad, Johanne; Johnson, Clare; De Clippele, Laurence Helene; Roberts, J Murray (2020): ATLAS Mingulay Reef Complex Macrobenthos and Environmental Data. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.915974	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.915974	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911552 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911551
IATL_DATA_0018	Kiko,Rainer (2019): Zooplankton-mediated fluxes in the Eastern Tropical North Atlantic. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.903023	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3357972	
IATL_DATA_0019	Langley, Beth; Halloran, Paul; Power, Ann; Rickaby, Rosalind; Chana, Prabhjoat; Diver, Poppy; Thornalley, David; Hacker, Christian; Love, John (2020). ImageStream Data of Isolating Cocospheres within Sediment [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3979045	https://zenodo.org/record/3979045	
IATL_DATA_0020	Lim, Aaron (2020): UCC Bathymetric and Backscatter grids of the Porcupine Abyssal Plain. University College Cork, PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.916052	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.916052	
IATL_DATA_0021	Mayorga-Adame, C. Gabriela (2022). NOC-MSM/LTRANS-for-NEMO (v0.0). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6092322	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6092322	
IATL_DATA_0022	Mohrmann, Jochen; Gazis, Iason-Zois; Schoening, Timm; Wöfl, Anne-Cathrin (2021): Multibeam bathymetry raw data (Kongsberg EM 122 entire dataset) of RV MARIA S. MERIAN during cruise MSM96. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.929091	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.929091	
IATL_DATA_0023	Nascimento, Rodrigo Azevedo; Santos, Thiago; Venancio, Igor Martins; Chiessi, Cristiano Mazur; Ballalai, João M; Kuhnert, Henning; Govin, Aline; Portilho-Ramos, Rodrigo Costa; Lessa, Douglas Villela de Oliveira; Dias, Bruna Borba; Pinho, Tainã Marcos Lima; Crivellari, Stefano; Mulitza, Stefan; Albuquerque, Ana Luiza (2021): Origin of $\delta^{13}C$ minimum events in	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.936785	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.936780 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.936784 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.936782 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.936783
IATL_DATA_0024	Perez, José Angel Alvarez; Sant'Ana, Rodrigo; Gavazzoni, Lucas; Varotto, Ricardo Silva; Sumida, Paulo Yukio Gomes; Lindner, Alberto; Bernardino, Angelo Fraga; Silva, Priscila Reis da; Holanda, Guarani Cavalcanti (2022): 3D seismic, multibeam and sonar interferometry scanning bathymetry data of Espirito Santo and Campos Basins - SW Atlantic	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.942382	
IATL_DATA_0025	Portilho-Ramos, Rodrigo Costa; Titschack, Jürgen; Wienberg, Claudia; Siccha, Michael; Yokoyama, Yusuke; Hebbeln, Dierk (2021): Major environmental drivers determining life and death of cold-water corals through time. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932775	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932775	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932737 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932760 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932719 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932703 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932720 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932746 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932759 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932701 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932727 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932716 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.932731
IATL_DATA_0026	Rakka, Maria; Maier, Sandra R.; van Oevelen, Dick; Bilan, Meri; Godinho, Antonio; Orejas, Covadonga; Carreiro-Silva, Marina (2020): Feeding biology of two common habitat-forming octocorals in the Azores Archipelago. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.913184	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.913184	
IATL_DATA_0027	Rakka, Maria; Godinho, Antonio; Orejas, Covadonga; Carreiro-Silva, Marina (2022): Embryo and larval biology of the deep-sea octocoral <i>Dentomuricea</i> aff. <i>meteor</i> from the Azores under two temperature regimes. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.942769	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.942769	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.942677 https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.942771 https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.942752 https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.942773
IATL_DATA_0028	Schoening, Timm; Gazis, Iason-Zois; Mohrmann, Jochen (2021): Sediment echosounder raw data (Atlas Parasound P70 echosounder entire dataset) of RV MARIA S. MERIAN during cruise MSM96. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.929548	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.929548	

IATL_DATA_0029	Schoening, Timm; Paul, Sophie Anna Luise (2021): CTD raw data files from Maria S. Merian cruise MSM96. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.928600 (dataset in review)	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.928600	
IATL_DATA_0030	Schulzki, Tobias, Getzlaff, Klaus, and Biastoch, Arne (2021). Supplementary Data to "On the variability of the DWBC transport between 26.5°N and 16°N in an eddy-rich ocean model" [dataset]. GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel [distributor].	https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12085/ec430a5c-1930-4a87-bb1f-973162c2a135	
IATL_DATA_0031	Stenvers, Vanessa; Hauss, Helena; Freitas, Rui; Neitzel, Philipp; Osborn, Karen; Robison, Bruce H; Hoving, Henk-Jan Ties (2020): Pyrosoma atlanticum in the eastern tropical North Atlantic (ETNA). PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918915	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918915	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.919326 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918870 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918907 https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.919340 https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.919327 https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.919341 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918914 https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.918916
IATL_DATA_0032	Van Audenhaege Loic, Matabos Marjolaine, Courant Valentin, Jaulin Emmanuel, Raffault Clarisse, Le Goffic Léa, Drugmand Jonathan, Brind'Amour Anik, Laes Agathe, Sarradin Pierre-Marie, Sarrazin Jozee (2022). Compilation of image annotations and environmental data of 7 years of monitoring of hydrothermal assemblages using the TEMPO ecological module (EMSO-	http://doi.org/10.17882/84672	
IATL_DATA_0033	Van Audenhaege Loic, Matabos Marjolaine, Gautier Laurent, Legrand Julien, Sarradin Pierre-Marie, Sarrazin Jozee (2022). Feature-matching based overlay of 7 years of high-resolution imagery collected by the TEMPO ecological module (EMSO-Azores observatory). SEANOE. https://doi.org/10.17882/87389	https://doi.org/10.17882/87389	
IATL_DATA_0034	Van Audenhaege, Loïc; Broad, Emmeline; Hendry, Katharine R; Huvenne, Veerle A I (2021): High-Resolution Vertical of a Deep-Sea Cliff offshore Greenland and the Associated Epibenthic Fauna. PANGAEA, https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.931687	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.931687	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.931680 https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.931684
IATL_DATA_0035	Schulzki, Tobias, Harlaß, Jan, Schwarzkopf, Franziska U., and Biastoch, Arne (2022). Towards ocean hindcasts in earth system models: AMOC variability in a partially coupled model at eddying resolution. [dataset]. GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel [distributor].	https://data.geomar.de/downloads/20.500.12085/57ea9d04-2bd4-4a27-8994-3e19982731bd/	
IATL_DATA_0036	Horton T (2019): Scavenging Amphipods, Porcupine Abyssal Plain Sustained Observatory, North Atlantic, 1985-2016. v1.2. The Discovery Collections. Dataset/Samplingevent. http://ipt.iobis.org/obis-deepsea/resource?r=pap_scavenging_amphipods&v=1.2 https://doi.org/10.15468/2akju5 accessed via GBIF.org on 2022-06-07.	https://doi.org/10.15468/2akju5	
IATL_DATA_0037	Selway, Caitlin Alyssa, Armbrecht, Linda, & Thornalley, David. (2021). Marine Sedimentary Ancient DNA (sedaDNA) from the North Atlantic Ocean [Data set]. Zenodo.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6342810	